

STUDY SKILLS AND ENGAGEMENT AS PREDICTORS OF STUDENTS' ACHIEVEMENT IN CHEMISTRY IN POST BASIC SCHOOLS IN GOMBE STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated study skills and engagement as predictors of students' academic achievement in Chemistry in post-basic schools in Gombe State, Nigeria. The study adopted a predictive correlation design. The population for the study comprised all the Chemistry students in SS III (2023/2024 session) in Gombe state totalling 10,533 of the 91 Chemistry-offering post basic schools within the 11 local government areas and three educational zones of the state. A sample of 370 SS III students were selected using multi-stage sampling technique to be respondents of the study. The instruments for data collection for this study were Chemistry Students' Study Skills and Engagement Questionnaire (CSSSEQ) adapted from DiPerna and Elliotts (2018) and Chemistry Results Proforma (CRP) for the collection of students' academic achievements. The CSSSEQ was trial tested and yielded an overall reliability index of 0.87 using the Cronbach's alpha. The data for the study were analyzed using descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) to answer the research questions one to three. While linear regression was used to test hypotheses one and two, and multiple regression analysis was used to test hypothesis three at 0.05 level of significance. The results revealed that study skills significantly predicted students' academic achievement in Chemistry $F(1, 368) = 7.409, p = 0.007$. Similarly, students' engagement also significantly predicted students' academic achievement in Chemistry $F(1, 368) = 11.428$ and $p = 0.001$. Based on the findings, it is recommended amongst others that teachers should adopt activities the enhance students' engagement, these activities can increase student engagement and subsequently improve their academic achievement.

Keywords: Study Skills, Engagement, Academic Achievement

INTRODUCTION

Science education plays a crucial role in shaping individuals' understanding of the natural world, fostering scientific literacy, and nurturing a spirit of inquiry. With the increasing complexity of scientific advancements and their impact on society, it is essential to equip learners with the necessary knowledge and skills to navigate the intricacies of the scientific domain. According to the Federal Government of Nigeria [FGN] (2014), science education is an integrated field of study that considers both the subject matter of science discipline such as Agriculture, Biology, Physics and Chemistry as requirements for study of various scientific fields in tertiary institutions.

Chemistry is one of the fundamental science subjects which plays a vital role in various fields such as Medicine, Pharmaceuticals, Engineering, and Environmental sciences. According to Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council [NERDC] (2012), the objectives of chemistry education at post-basic Schools include: providing the students with basic knowledge in chemical concepts and principles through efficient selection of content sequencing; showing inter-relationships between Chemistry and other science subjects and providing a reasonable and adequate foundation for a Chemistry course at tertiary level. Chemistry education holds a significant position within the broader scope of science education, as it provides essential insights into the composition, properties, and transformations of matter. Nleonu and Ezeibe (2020) reported that Chemistry education is needed for development, technological emancipation and industrial expansion. It is therefore, necessary that students at post basic level should understand the subject very well, so that they can perform better in examinations.

Despite the importance of Chemistry in everyday life, a report of West African Senior Secondary Certificate Examinations (WASSCE) shows that 77.02%, 89.89 and 85.45% of students scored grades of A1-C6 in Chemistry in the WAEC May/June 2019, 2020 and 2021 respectively. However, despite the good achievement nationwide, a report from Gombe State Ministry of Education shows that 73%, 68%, 64% and 61% of students who sat for WAEC in 2019, 2020, 2021 and 2022 respectively have not made a credit pass in chemistry. Although, the trend shows a slight improvement within the four years observed, however, more than 60% every year didn't get the university requirement in the subject. This alarming trend has become a great threat to the state's future and survival in terms of science and technology developments. These poor achievements have been attributed to factors like study skills and students' engagement.

Study skill is a technique that will help a student in studying, recalling, and retaining information. It encompasses a range of techniques and strategies that students can employ to enhance their learning and comprehension of academic material. These skills include time management, active reading strategies, note-taking techniques, critical thinking, and exam preparation methods (Bhasin, 2021). These skills, in fact, help the students to make better use of study hours. Hence, given the positive role of study skills in students' academic achievement and better learning, assessment of students' study skills and their satisfaction with study skills are of high significance. Naqvi, Chikwa, Menon and Al Kharusi (2018) argue that lack of study skills puts students at a disadvantage because they suffer tremendously at various stages of their academic career. Such students are often victims of procrastination, overconfidence, mismanagement, and stress.

Several studies were carried out on study skills and students' academic achievement. For example, Siraj, Shah and Khan (2021) carried out a study on the relationship between study skills and academic achievement of University students. The results showed that students usually used study skills, and there was no significant relationship found between study skills and academic achievement of students. Another study by Israel and Bahago (2020) investigated the effects of study skills training on achievement in mathematics of low achieving upper basic students in Plateau State, Nigeria. Findings from the study revealed that prior to intervention, the Upper Basic Students had low study skills and achievement in Mathematics, but improved in both areas after exposure to study skills training. Furthermore, Shackebaei, et al. (2015) investigated study skills and their correlation with academic satisfaction and achievement among medical and pharmacy students in Kermanshah University of Medical Sciences. The finding revealed that a significantly positive correlation was observed between students' study skills and their Grade Point Average (GPA) of previous term ($r=0.269$, $P=0.001$) and satisfaction with study skills ($r=0.493$, $P=0.001$). In summary, the acquisition and application of study skills not only contribute to immediate academic success but also motivate the students during learning process.

Apart from study skills, another important enabler of academic achievement is students' engagement. According to Gunuc and Kuzu (2014) maintained that class engagement involves students' cognitive, emotional and behavioral responses to in-class and out-of-class activities. Moreover, Sukor, Ayub, Ab Rashid and Abdul Halim (2021) student engagement refers to the time and energy students devote to educationally sound activities inside and outside of the classroom. The time and energy students commit to educationally sound activities, whether within or outside the classroom, play a pivotal role in their personal and academic growth. Furthermore, Peters, Zdravkovic, Costa, Celenza and Ghias (2019) maintained that student engagement refers to actively involvement by students in their assignments and learning activities. students' involvement in assignments and other learning activities is essential for their academic growth and development. It promotes active learning, skill development, practical application of knowledge, and a sense of ownership over one's education. Encouraging and facilitating such involvement is a key aspect of effective teaching and promoting academic achievement.

Numerous studies explored the intricate relationship between student engagement and academic achievement across various educational levels and disciplines. For example, Similarly, Fredricks, Blumenfeld, and Paris (2020) revealed a strong relationship between students' engagement and academic achievement across multiple studies and diverse populations. Masila (2022) examined academic engagement and learning approaches as predictors of academic achievement from three students in Machakos County, Kenya. The multiple correlation coefficient was 0.37 which indicates that the independent variables moderately predict academic achievement. R square was 0.14 implying that 14% variance in academic achievement is explained by cognitive engagement, emotional engagement, deep approach and surface approach. Also, a study by Amoah, Britwum, Acheampong and Sefah (2021) carry out an analysis of the relationship between students' engagement and academic achievement in college of education students in Ghana. The result showed that all the variables (behavioural, emotional and cognitive) had relationships with academic achievement with emotional recording a negative correlation coefficient ($r = -.059$, $p = .151$). A study by Sukor, Ayub, Ab Rashid and Abdul Halim (2021) examined the relationship between students' engagement with academic performance among non-food science students. Results showed significant positive relationship between overall students' engagements with academic performance ($r = 0.312$; $p < 0.001$). Moreover, Surum (2018) investigated student academic engagement and the academic achievement of form one students in Dadaab refugee camp, Kenya. The results showed that 65% of the variation in form one students' test score can be explained by their level of academic engagement. The results indicate that student academic engagement is a predictor of form one students' test score. Furthermore, Wara, Aloka and Odongo (2018) investigated the relationship between cognitive engagement and academic achievement among Kenyan secondary school students. The study revealed that cognitive engagement was a significant predictor of academic achievement among secondary school students studied ($r=.376$, $N=312$, $p = .01$).

Based on the forgoing, researcher observed that many studies within and outside Nigeria revealed that factors like study skills (Israel & Bahago, 2020; Motevalli, Hamzah, Roslan, & Hamzah, 2021), engagement (Amoah, Britwum, Acheampong, & Sefah, 2021; Delfino, 2019; Konold, Cornell, Jia, & Malone, 2018) and are potent predictors of academic achievement. However, empirical evidence shows that none of the study investigated the influence of these factors jointly on students' academic achievement in Chemistry in Gombe State. These therefore, necessitated the current researcher to investigate study skills and engagement as predictors of students' academic achievement in Chemistry in Post-Basic Schools in Gombe State, Nigeria.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of this study is to determine the extent to which academic enablers predict students' academic achievement in chemistry in post basic schools of Gombe State. Specifically, the study sought to;

- i. determine whether students' study skill predicts post basic school students' academic achievement in chemistry in Gombe State, Nigeria.
- ii. determine whether student's engagement predicts post basic school students' academic achievement in chemistry in Gombe State, Nigeria.
- iii. Determine the mean academic achievement score of students in Chemistry in post basic schools in Gombe State, Nigeria.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research questions were raised to guide the study;

- i. What is the level of students' study skills in post basic schools in Gombe State, Nigeria?
- ii. What is the level of students' engagement in post basic schools in Gombe State, Nigeria?
- iii. What is the mean academic achievement score of students in Chemistry in post basic schools in Gombe State, Nigeria?

HYPOTHESES

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- H₀₁:** Students' study skills do not significantly predict academic achievement in chemistry
- H₀₂:** Students' engagements do not significantly predict academic achievement in chemistry
- H₀₃:** study skills and engagement do not significantly predict students' academic achievement in chemistry

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE REVIEW

Student success in chemistry, often viewed as a challenging subject, is intricately connected to a complex interplay of cognitive and affective factors (King, 2022; Ross et al., 2019). Recent research highlights the critical role of study skills and engagement as key predictors of academic achievement in chemistry (Collini et al., 2023; Srinivasan, 2017). Chemistry education research has delved into various affective factors—such as attitudes, self-efficacy, motivation, and emotions—to understand their impact on student performance (Flaherty, 2020). Numerous studies have sought to uncover the reasons behind unsatisfactory performances among undergraduate chemistry students in both cognitive and affective domains (George et al., 2021).

Moreover, student engagement, which includes behavioral, emotional, and cognitive dimensions, emerges as a significant predictor of academic success (Hao et al., 2018). Effective study skills, including time management, note-taking, and active learning strategies, equip students with the necessary tools to navigate the complexities of chemistry coursework (Frost et al., 2024). Notably, motivation and specific study techniques have been linked to enhanced academic performance (Hora & Oleson, 2017). In fact, research indicates that students who actively engage in their studies tend to achieve more positive outcomes compared to their unmotivated peers (Zhao et al., 2021).

The correlation between student engagement and academic achievement in chemistry is well-documented (González et al., 2020). Engagement transcends mere attendance; it encompasses a student's psychological investment in learning (Zepke

& Leach, 2010). This can manifest through curiosity, asking relevant questions, helping to maintain a tidy lab environment, and collaborating with peers to ensure a comprehensive understanding of the material.

Furthermore, a study by Enekwechi and Ezeanya (2021) examined how study habits predict chemistry achievement among secondary school students in Anambra state, revealing that study habits accounted for a notable portion of academic performance. The most significant contributors were note-taking, reading, and test preparation habits. This current study also focuses on study skills and engagement as predictors of chemistry achievement, specifically in post-basic schools in Gombe State, Nigeria, highlighting the relevance of effective study habits for student success.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a predictive correlation design. Predictive correlational research design is used to forecast the amount of prediction of one or more variables on another variable(s) (Sani, 2017). The population for the study comprised all the SS III students in Chemistry in (2023/2024 session) in Gombe state totaling 10,038 of the 71 Chemistry-offering post basic schools within the 11 Local Government Areas and three educational zones of the state. The sample size of this study was 370 SS III students in Chemistry in post basic schools of Gombe State who were selected to participate in the study using a simple random sampling and stratified random sampling techniques. This sample size is based on (Adam, 2020) who recommended the sample size of 370 for 10,000 finite population at all 95% of confidence.

The instruments for data collection for this study were Chemistry Students' Study Skills and Engagement Questionnaire (CSSSEQ) and Chemistry Result Proforma (CRP). The CSAEQ was validated and yielded a reliability index of 0.79, and 0.83, for study skills and engagement subscales respectively using Cronbach's Alpha statistic.

The data collected for this study were analyzed using both descriptive statistics and inferential statistics. Research question 1, 2, and 3, were analyzed using descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) to find the level of students' study skills and engagement. While the formulated hypotheses were tested using Linear and Multiple regression analysis. Linear regression was used to test hypotheses 1 and 2, while hypothesis 3 was tested using multiple regression at 0.05 level of significance. If the p-value was less than 0.05 the null hypothesis was rejected, otherwise the null hypothesis was not rejected. All the data analyses were computed using statistical software SPSS version 26.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: What is the level of students' study skills in post basic schools in Gombe State, Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Responses of Respondents on Level of Students' Study Skills in Post Basic Schools in Gombe State, Nigeria

S/N	Item (n = 370)	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Manage time to study my Chemistry books	3.33	1.10	ML
2	Actively read my Chemistry notebooks	3.35	1.16	ML
3	Taking note when my Chemistry teacher explaining a concept	3.36	1.19	ML
4	Correcting my work in Chemistry without being asked	3.27	1.24	ML
5	Follow instructions on my Chemistry assignments	3.74	1.19	HL
6	Underlining parts that I think are important When reading Chemistry books	3.35	1.25	ML
7	Survey a topic before I begin reading my Chemistry notebook	3.32	1.24	ML
8	Reviewing my Chemistry past exam questions several times in a term	3.40	1.18	ML

9	Utilizing study aids such as models and concept maps, to enhance my understanding of chemistry	3.27	1.28	ML
10	Getting a good night's rest prior to a scheduled examination	3.75	2.49	HL
11	Trying to imagine possible test questions during preparation for my Chemistry examination	3.92	1.17	HL
12	Applying critical thinking skills when solving problems in Chemistry	3.86	1.13	HL
Grand Mean		3.49	1.30	ML

Key: n = Number of participants, HL = High Level, ML = Moderate Level, SD, Standard Deviation

The results in Table 1 indicate that Items 5, 10, 11, and 12 are categorized as having a high level (HL) of study skills, though most of the items fall into the moderate level (ML), with means ranging from 3.27 to 3.40. This includes: Managing time (3.33) and actively reading notebooks (3.35), which are fundamental skills but suggest that students may need to enhance their time management strategies and reading comprehension. The standard deviations (SD) vary across items, with the highest (2.49) for the item about getting a good night's rest. This suggests a significant disparity in how students perceive the importance of rest before exams, indicating that while some prioritize this, others may not. The grand mean of 3.49 indicates a moderate level (ML) of study skills among respondents. This suggests that while students in post-basic schools in Gombe State, possess some effective study habits, there is room for improvement.

Research Question 2: What is the level of students' engagement in post basic schools in Gombe State, Nigeria?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Responses of Respondents on Level of Students' Engagement in Post Basic Schools in Gombe State, Nigeria

S/N	Item (n = 370)	Mean	SD	Remark
13	Asking questions in Chemistry lessons	3.62	1.23	HL
14	Participation in class discussions during Chemistry lessons	3.64	1.26	HL
15	volunteer to answer questions during Chemistry lessons	3.48	1.20	ML
16	Involvement in Chemistry class activities	3.78	2.79	HL
17	Volunteer to responds to questions asked in Chemistry class	3.69	1.10	HL
18	Initiating conversations of Chemistry with classmates	3.73	2.91	HL
19	Making effort to link the information I learn in one chemistry lesson to what I learn in lesson in other classes	3.55	3.58	HL
20	spending a lot of time looking for more information on topics discussed in chemistry lessons.	3.41	1.19	ML
21	Regretting missing my chemistry lectures	3.81	1.26	HL
22	Working with my classmates to solve problem in Chemistry	3.70	1.25	HL
23	Arriving early for chemistry classes	3.76	1.24	HL
24	completing chemistry assignments and other school-related tasks on time	3.76	1.17	HL
25	Utilizing critical thinking skills in balancing chemical equations	3.46	1.16	ML
Grand Mean		3.65	1.64	HL

Key: n = Number of participants, HL = High Level, ML = Moderate Level, SD, Standard Deviation

The table 2 provides the mean and standard deviation of responses from 370 respondents regarding their engagement in Chemistry classes.

Several items reflect high engagement: Involvement in class activities (Mean: 3.78) and regretting missed lectures (Mean: 3.81) highlight strong commitment and a desire to participate in chemistry classes. Participation in discussions (Mean: 3.64) and asking questions (Mean: 3.62) indicate that students feel comfortable interacting during lessons. However some items such as volunteering to answer questions (Mean: 3.48) and linking information from different lessons (Mean: 3.55) are rated at a moderate level (ML). This suggests that while students are engaged, there is potential for enhancing their confidence in answering and connecting concepts.

The standard deviations show notable variability, particularly in items like involvement in class activities (SD: 2.79) and linking information (SD: 3.58). This indicates differing levels of engagement and understanding among students, suggesting that some may struggle with active participation or integrating knowledge across subjects. The grand mean of 3.65 indicates a high level (HL) of engagement among students. This suggests that students in post-basic schools in Gombe State, are actively participating and involved in their Chemistry lesson.

Research Question 3: What is the mean of academic achievement of students in Chemistry in post basic schools in Gombe State, Nigeria?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of academic achievement of students in post basic schools in Gombe State, Nigeria

	N	Mean	SD	Remark
Mean achievement score	370	41.42	13.814	Pass

Table 3 revealed that the mean achievement score of academic achievement in Chemistry of post basic schools' students in Gombe State, Nigeria is 41.42 and standard deviation of 13.814. this implies that the mean academic achievement score is below pass mark of 50% (credit).

H₀₁: Students' study skills do not significantly predict academic achievement in chemistry

Table 4a: Summary of ANOVA results from Regression Analysis of Prediction between Students' Study Skills and Academic Achievement in Chemistry

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1376.850	1	1376.850	7.409	.007 ^b
	Residual	68386.827	368	185.834		
	Total	69763.677	369			

a. Dependent Variable: Students' Academic Achievement

b. Predictors: (Constant), Students' study skills in learning Chemistry

Results of Analysis in Table 4a reveals that Students' Study Skills is a significant Predictor of academic achievement in Chemistry, $F(1, 368) = 7.409, p < 0.05$. Since the p – value (0.007) is less than 0.05 alpha level, it is concluded that the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that students' study skills significantly predict academic achievement in chemistry.

Table 4b: Model Summary results from Regression Analysis of Prediction between Students' Study Skills and Academic Achievement in Chemistry

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.140 ^a	.020	.017	13.63209

a. Predictors: (Constant), Students' study skills in learning Chemistry

The result in Table 4b shows a model summary which shows how the independent variable explains the variance in the dependent variable. The adjusted R-square shows that Students' study skills explained 1.7% of the variance in students' academic achievement in Chemistry.

Table 4c: Coefficient of Beta results from Regression Analysis of Prediction between Students' Study Skills and Academic Achievement in Chemistry

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	49.013	3.091		15.855	.000
	Students' study skills in learning Chemistry	-2.279	.837	-.140	-2.722	.007

a. Dependent Variable: Students' Academic Achievement

The result in Table 4c indicates the Beta coefficient of the regression analysis of Students' study skills and students' academic achievement in Chemistry. The result shows a beta coefficient of ($\beta = -0.140, t = -2.722, p = 0.007$). This indicates that Students' study skills are a significant predictor of academic achievement with 14.0% contribution to its explanation.

H₀₂: Students' engagements do not significantly predict academic achievement in chemistry

Table 5a: Summary of ANOVA results from Regression Analysis of Prediction between Students' Engagement in Learning Chemistry and Academic Achievement in Chemistry

	Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2101.167	1	2101.167	11.428	.001 ^b
	Residual	67662.509	368	183.866		
	Total	69763.677	369			

a. Dependent Variable: Students' Academic Achievement

b. Predictors: (Constant), Students' engagement in learning Chemistry

Results of Analysis in Table 5a reveals that students' engagement is a significant Predictor of academic achievement in Chemistry $F(1, 368) = 11.428$ and $p < 0.05$. Given that the p-value (0.001) falls below the alpha level of 0.05, the null

hypothesis is rejected, suggesting that students' engagement in learning chemistry significantly predicts their academic achievement in the subject.

Table 5b: Model Summary results from Regression Analysis of Prediction between Students' Engagement in Learning Chemistry and Academic Achievement in Chemistry

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.174 ^a	.030	.027	13.55970

a. Predictors: (Constant), Students' engagement in learning Chemistry

The outcome presented in Table 5b provides a model summary illustrating how the independent variable accounts for the variability in the dependent variable. Specifically, the result indicates that students' engagement in learning chemistry accounted for 2.7% of the variance in students' academic achievement in Chemistry.

Table 5c: Coefficient of Beta results from Regression Analysis of Prediction between Students' Engagement in Learning Chemistry and Academic Achievement in Chemistry

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	49.876	2.769		18.009	.000
	Students' engagement in learning Chemistry	-2.555	.756	-.174	-3.380	.001

a. Dependent Variable: Students' Academic Achievement

Table 5c presents the findings of a regression analysis linking students' study skills to their academic performance in Chemistry. The analysis reveals a beta coefficient of ($\beta = -0.174, t = -3.380, p = 0.001$). These results suggest that students' active involvement in learning Chemistry is a meaningful predictor of their academic achievement with 17.4% contribution rate.

H₀₃: Study skills and engagement do not significantly predict students' academic achievement in chemistry

Table 6a: Summary of ANOVA results from Regression Analysis of Prediction between Students' study skills and engagement and Academic Achievement in Chemistry

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2720.271	2	1360.135	5.144	.006 ^b
	Residual	97030.244	367	264.388		
	Total	99750.514	369			

a. Dependent Variable: Students' Academic Achievement

b. Predictors: (Constant), Students' study skills in learning Chemistry, Students' engagement in learning Chemistry

The analysis in Table 6a provides a summary of the regression analysis predicting academic achievement in Chemistry based on students' Academic Enablers. The results indicate that academic enablers, including study skills, and engagement are significant predictors of academic achievement in Chemistry, $F(2, 367) = 5.144, p < 0.05$. As the p-value (0.006) is below the alpha level of 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating that Students study skills and engagement do indeed significantly predict academic achievement in Chemistry.

Table 6b: Model Summary from Regression Analysis of Prediction between Students' Academic Enablers and Academic Achievement in Chemistry

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.165 ^a	.027	.022	16.26000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Students' study skills in learning Chemistry, Students' engagement in learning Chemistry

The result in Table 6b shows a model summary which shows how the independent variable explains the variance in the dependent variable. The adjusted R square shows that Academic enablers (study skills and engagement) jointly explained 2.2% of the variance in students' academic achievement in Chemistry.

Table 6c: Coefficient of Beta from Regression Analysis of Prediction between Students' Academic Enablers and Academic Achievement in Chemistry

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Coefficients		
1	(Constant)	58.555	5.108		11.463	.000
	Students' study skills in learning Chemistry	.354	.114	.203	3.111	.002
	Students' engagement in learning Chemistry	-.168	.130	-.084	-1.288	.199

a. Dependent Variable: Students' Academic Achievement

The regression analysis results indicate that students' study skills in learning Chemistry have a statistically significant positive effect on their academic achievement ($B = 0.354, \beta = 0.203, t = 3.111, p = 0.002$), suggesting that students' study skills lead to higher achievement. However, students' engagement in learning Chemistry does not show a significant relationship with academic achievement ($B = -0.168, \beta = -0.084, t = -1.288, p = 0.199$). This implies that variations in engagement levels do not significantly predict academic performance.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The result of this study revealed that students' study skills in learning chemistry is moderate, and it significantly predict students' academic achievement in chemistry in post basic schools in Gombe state. This finding suggests that only a modest portion of the variance in academic Achievement can be attributed to study skills, indicating that other factors likely

play a substantial role in influencing students' academic Achievement in chemistry. This finding is in agreement with Shackebaei, et al. (2015) who reported a significantly positive correlation was observed between students' study skills and their Grade Point Average. Also, with Rahim and Moen (2013) who reported that study skills such as test taking, note taking, and analytical thinking and problem-solving skills were positively correlated with GPA achievement. This may be due to the fact that Chemistry, as a subject, often involves intricate concepts, detailed problem-solving, and the application of theoretical knowledge to practical scenarios. However, the finding in the present study is in contrast with Siraj, Shah and Khan (2021) who reported that there is no significant relationship found between study skills and academic achievement of students. This may probably because in their study they used University students in Pakistan who may have high academic task compared to post basic school students.

Additionally, the result also revealed that students' engagement in learning chemistry is high, and it significantly predict students' academic achievement in chemistry in post basic schools in Gombe state. This finding suggests that only a small portion of the variance in academic Achievement in Chemistry can be attributed to engagement, indicating that other factors may likely play a substantial role in influencing students' academic Achievement in chemistry. This finding is in line with Masila (2022) who reported that cognitive engagement and academic achievement had a positive significant correlation. Also, with Sukor, Ayub, Ab Rashid and Abdul Halim (2021) who reported a significant positive relationship between overall students' engagements with academic Achievement. However, the finding is in contrast with Amoah, Britwum, Acheampong and Sefah (2021) who reported that the variables (behavioral, emotional and cognitive engagement) were not significant in predicting academic achievement of College of Education students in Ghana. This may be due to the difference in the location and level of participants. the students in the college of education may have different level of engagement and high academic task compared to post basic school used in the present study. Finally, the finding also revealed that study skills and engagement jointly predicted students' academic achievement in chemistry in post basic schools in Gombe state.

CONCLUSION

The study found that academic enablers, including study skills and engagement, are significant predictors of academic achievement in Chemistry among post-basic school students in Gombe State. Although students demonstrate moderate study skills and a high level of engagement in Chemistry classes, there are opportunities for enhancing their confidence and participation. By focusing on these areas for improvement, students can achieve better academic outcomes and deepen their understanding of the subject.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. To enhance study skills, it would be helpful for government to organize specific workshops or training sessions that concentrate on students' time management, active reading, and effective note-taking techniques. Furthermore, highlighting the significance of rest and mental readiness can boost students' performance.
2. To further increase student engagement, chemistry teachers might adopt methods that promote more interactive participation, like group projects or peer teaching. Creating an atmosphere where students are encouraged to connect chemistry ideas across various subjects could also improve their overall comprehension.

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